

The Poetry of Syed Ali Hamid: An Evaluation

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Indian Contemporary Poetry in English is rich in form and contents. No doubt, the weeds in the form of poetasters crowd out the genuine poetic flowers but the scythe of Time pulls them out and thus provides space for the growth of the genuine ones. Syed Ali Hamid (1954) is such a genuine poetic flower, known for naturalness, cosmopolitan vision and loving heart. Though he registered his presence with *Autumn Rainbow* (1993), he came to full bloom with *The Ontology of Desire: New and Selected Poems* (2015), which, besides new poems, contains selected poems from his earlier collections including *No Man's Land* (2003) and *Desire, Ultimately* (2013).

Hamid's poetry is always rooted in the sensuous world. It is intensely realistic, sometimes erotic and never boring. He handles his language and technique with an ease that gives his poetry its stubborn quality. He is careful enough not to make his verse pedantic, which we encounter in much of today's poetry. His poetry is a way of struggling with life's dark meanings, its uncompromising postures. It is always ready to face the world of dilemmas and fears, of the neglected maneuverings of the body and the soul. It is always a pleasure to read his work. (Blurb)

This is what Bibhu Padhi writes about Hamid's poetry. His nurturing amidst the decadent Avadh aristocracy in Lucknow gives him "refined manners and extreme politeness in conversation." Lucknow is famous everywhere for its Lacknavi culture. It is strange that the people see and appreciate the flowers of other gardens but remain unknown to the fragrant flowers of their own garden. The case of Hamid is not his case only but mostly of every poet who remains unknown to the people of his own place. Somewhere the poet associates himself with the place of his birth and traces the seed of his identity.

People recognize my city
wherever I go,
but in my own city I have become
a stranger,
a vestigial organ. (46)

Desire is the seed from which the poetic saplings spring, bloom and spread their fragrance. The poet's knack is in making abstract concrete and concrete abstract. As a creator, he creates the ontology of desire, which seems to have its existence. Desire becomes a being and begins to have conversation with the poet in Hamid. Sometimes it seems that he is lost in the world of desire which conceals thousands of layers of desires within. His longing is the longing for desire within desire. He is a poet of desire's desire. Here is an excerpt which reveals two levels—physical and metaphysical. Whether desire is beloved or beloved desire becomes a mystery which the poet attempts to create in the concrete form.

as she sips her whisky,
my hands relaxing her body
neck to the toes,
the whispers of my heart
the commands of my brain
guiding my hands;
her eyes
intoxicated with whisky and desire
and her perfect lips
breaking into a smile
my only reward.(20)

Desire is studied and observed from the metaphysical viewpoints. The abstract becomes concrete. Desire gives birth to desire. The being of desire appears before the poet who feels himself rewarded when a smile floats. Here is the process how desire takes birth:

In the dark region of the mind
desire takes birth
like a rainbow
piercing a grey cloud
and once perceived
is nourished
sometimes flirted with
beneath the indulgent veneer
of respectability.(139)

“As a man thinketh in his heart, so is he” is a proverb. Hamid goes one step further and states “my desire will awaken my destiny”(24) and does not mind if it annihilates his identity provided that it creates ecstasy. Desire makes destiny. The abstract is translated into the concrete. The poet is honest thoroughly and does not feel shame when he declares: “I burnt in the fire of desire/and sometimes naked lust”(60). Desires are desire and they will remain as they are. What one needs is the sublimation. The poet always recommends for the sublimation though sometimes he doubts how he will be purified when he is still burning with desire. Man is mortal but the soul is immortal. How souls, despite their indulgence in lust, will be purified is the question. Mark the doubtful nature when the poet interrogates:

Can we console ourselves
with the immortality
of our sodomized souls?
Can they be purified
after so many years in a brothel
where we pump our semen
into each other’s rectum?(69)

The poet longs for sublimation but the moment he thinks of cross, love, parting, death and the like, he begins to have doubts and fails to understand how to come out of the dilemma and where to go. Mark the lines for the natural flow of feelings that start flowing in words:

Wherever I go
I carry my cross
So many loves
so many partings
some deception, some emotion,
some conglomeration, some alchemy.
After so many deaths,
so many resurrections
where do I go from here?(69)

The poet talks of kundalini awakening when he feels a desire within. It is rainbow like that originates “from the middle” while “travelling upwards/ later translated/ into preferences/ some particular/ some holistic”(119). He meditates and attempts to connect himself with his inner being through silence for the sublimation of his love into the divine one. Here is an excerpt which clearly reveals the images that begin to dance on the screen of his mind the moment he sits for meditation:

Then the concept
of communication through silence
the ecstasy of soul-union
divine love
dhyanam, third eye
the beyond.

But how long this illusion
this auto-suggestion?
The moment the eyes closed
for *dhyanam*
faces appeared
bodies, lips
breasts, cunts
groping hands
caressing feet
And the soul evaporated
into desire,
ultimately.(119)

The poet is honest enough to admit the hindrances that come on his way while undertaking inner journey. The inner journey gives a clue to understand one’s self. This is what counts. The appearance of faces and the parts of the bodies lead his ‘Self’ not to *dhyanam* but to the world of desire where he is lost while sensing the needs of his desire. The soul disappears the moment the body appears. What he needs is to decipher the language of desire and work accordingly. He never thinks of its suppression which leads to danger zone but begins to play with the close images which dance on the screen of his mind. He feels satisfied and comes to a peaceful state of mind as he has made his self inquiry. This *dhyanam* gives him an insight which offers him peace within. This is what makes the poet courageous enough to ask the question:

Will you ever synchronize
with my erotic desires,
respond
to my yearnings of pain and pleasure,
my ecstasy of surrender
to your immaculate beauty?(25)

The poet loves his beloved and begins to burn with the yearning—yearning for “the warmth of (your) body/for tears of happiness/to mingle with”(99) hers to feel one with her. The miracle occurs when the desire in her look becomes an envelope which envelops him and gives warmth of love while moderating the lust. He composes the song of love and sings it naturally and rhythmically:

The stirring of desire
in your look
envelops me in warmth
and your touch tones down
violent lust
softly, softly,
so very softly. (103)

Desire creates hope and hope gives him a new life. The poet in Hamid loves Nature and so likes to connect desire with Nature. He sees that the shower of rain revives and heals a dying tree. The desire, like a shower of rain, also heals, revives and does miracles. It makes the man see beauty everywhere and in everything. Mark the excerpt which reveals the interrelationship of Nature with desire:

But what about desire?
When a shower of rain
falls on a dying tree
it revives, heals,
rejuvenates with the power,
the magic of beauty.(29)

Desire becomes a passing shower which rekindles hope in the poet so powerfully that he connects it with life and its music. Mark the lines which give him a message of hope through Nature.

And suddenly again a passing shower
cools the earth
even if for a while
rekindling desire
rebuilding hope.
And what is life worth,
after all,
without the symphonies
of passing showers?(102)

His mind becomes intuitive because of the yearning for desire. He has become mature enough to take decision in life. He longs for growing his wings for flying with desire to touch the highest summit. A person without desire is dead. It is desire which makes him alive while giving strength to his wings for flight with confidence.

Growing up
is to grow wings
and learn to fly
with the desire
to touch the sky.(90)

The poet feels sad at the decline of the feeling of love and its confinement to the physical pleasures. Love that leads to physical pleasure without satisfying the very spirit is not love at all. He yearns for the old days when love was considered to be divine. Now matter matters, not love. The poet longs for the golden old days thus:

There was a time
when love was everything
a look, a touch, an ecstasy
all-important, pervasive.(70)

If desires give meaning to life, memories rub balm on the disturbed mind. Here is an excerpt about memories which prove to be a bridge between two hearts:

Memories jostle each other
to resurface
bridge the distance
lessen the pain
rejuvenate the mind.(108)

When the poet suffers much and bears “pain, sorrow, suffering”, he begins to interrogate the existence of God. Why does He enjoy giving pain to others? But the very nature of belief chides and makes him believe in God. God becomes a refuge. It does not matter if it is his pretence. Here are the lines which prove his doubt as well as his make-believe.

If yes, is He as sadist
enjoying Himself
at the expense of others?
But he still wanted
to believe in God
if only to use this as a quilt
to wriggle in when it was cold,
a refuge
even if one
of make-believe.(92)

The poet fails to find the way out of the jungle of adverse circumstances. The night becomes darker and he longs for a moonray to find his way but he finds that “there is only/the cradle of despair”(89) to make him sleep. He thinks that:

Perhaps only death
will bring to an end
this struggle with words
this struggle with tears.(100)

No doubt he uses words but feels that they have also become victims. Sometimes his words become so potent that they “break the barrier/and are answered/with the deep-sea look” and give him desire that makes him young enough to struggle.

with words that enter the blood,
and the familiar longing returns
making me young
once again.(105)

Now he feels the effect of his words which make his heart say that the beloved will sympathize him with her body and “bring an end/to this wordless agony”(141). The body, no doubt, will bring an end to agony. Her words prove to be rain. What rain is to the dried leaves, her words are to the lover.

Your words fell like rain
on parched earth
each drop absorbed
in the pores of my skin
waking from oblivion of dying,
slowly dying,
the dried roots
with the promise of leaves.(22)

These are the words which become panacea for sustaining his life in future. They are not merely words but have taken the form of poems which echo music of his soul. The poems make him travel in his past years to have the gems of sweet memories which will sustain him in future.

The words become poems
and the echoes music
as we trek into the past
to sustain
an uncertain future.(108)

Hamid is a poet of desire and intuition. He is spontaneous and fresh. Artificiality fails to touch him. His poems flow like the water of the river Ganga—pure and mysterious. Urdu orientation enters his poems. He succeeds in creating an innovative idiom, which becomes the fusion of Urdu and English in form and Hindustani or Indian in contents. In his poems he uses Urdu words and sometimes couplets at the beginning of his poems. For instance:

Aaye kuch abr kuch sharaab aaye(132)
To phir ae sangdil tera hi sang-e-aastan kyon ho?(133)

Hamid has also, very successfully, written a ghazal in English, which has the formal components of the Urdu ghazal like *radif*, *qafia*, *matla*, *maqta*, etc. Here is an excerpt which reveals the impact of Urdu idiom, replete with sensuous feelings that directly pierce the heart and intoxicate the mind:

Between your thighs was nectar from Paradise

I drank and knew, death could do no harm that night.(120)

No doubt, composing poem is an art which must be learnt. But the inner inspiration is what counts in the poetic process. While talking to Jaydeep Sarangi in an interview for *Poetcrit*, he frankly admits: “Certainly, the craft of poetry has to be learnt and mastered, but the primary thing is poetic inspiration, sensitivity and expression of myriad shades of feelings and emotions.” The poet in him is master craftsman who takes care of content and form. He is innovative in the use of phraseology which reveals its scenic beauty. “A bagful of memories”(76), “a feudal past”(34), “The inertia of survival”(81), “the orgasmic surrender/to eternity”(87), “jasmine-fragrant pubic hair”(87), “computerized movements”(88), “tears of severance”(104), “adulterate flashbacks”(106) etc., are the instances to prove the poet’s skill in using picturesque phrases. He attempts to fill his poems with Indianness and for this he uses Hindi, Sanskrit and Urdu words like *Imambara*(35), *sherwani*(36), *hoors*(42), *pati-parmeshwar*(43), *khus*(45), *ashrams*(47), *Mushairas*(49), *kavi sammelans*(49), *gulmohar*(61), *dhyanam*(119), *purdah*(130), *haya*, *sharm*(130), *sarangi*(40), *ghungroo*(40), *payaled feet*(138) and the like. Questioning technique also adds a charm to his poetry. The poet in Hamid knows how to use the technique of questioning to raise the curiosity of the reader who also associates himself with the poet. Here are a few instances to prove his art of questioning:

And what is life worth,
after all,
without the symphonies
of passing showers?(102)
....

Why is it so
that after the ripples
after the waves
there is only silence
just loneliness
with memories pricking the heart
softly, softly,
so very softly?(104)

The poet in Hamid knows how to make his poems beautiful with figures. He uses figures so naturally that they do not create artificiality which often weakens the effect.

Instance of simile:

Sometimes my words
whispered in the dark
touch a wall and return

like ejaculation
inside a condom.(105)

Instance of metaphor:

There's a woman in my blood
and her dusky face in my eyes.(58)

Instance of a sensuous fusion of figures like simile, metaphor and personification:

Your words fell like rain
on parched earth
each drop absorbed
in the pores of my skin
waking from oblivion of dying,
slowly dying,
the dried roots
with the promise of leaves.(22)

Instances of paradoxical nature:

Keep me in your bondage,
because in that
lies my freedom.(21)
....
And, of course, I remember you
the moment
I forget you.(142)

The poetic fabric of Hamid's poetry is woven with different kinds of threads. Places like Lucknow and Almora, nature related things like rain, autumn, rainbow, storm, clouds, forest etc., abstract subjects like hope, mystery, death, God, destiny, love, desire etc., festivals like mohurrum, and relatives like nawabs, grandfather etc., often appear in his poems.

While evaluating Hamid's poems, Jayanta Mahapatra finds them "existential, both in terms of life's experiences and in the philosophical sense of the quest for meaning in an indifferent world" (Blurb). The poet, sometimes, feels: "the funeral procession of words/leading nowhere" (101). But he waits and knows the outcome of waiting—waiting "of pain/of hope/of passionate anticipation" (25). The words take the form of a poem which becomes a cathartic therapy for him.

The poems that pierce
through a longing heart
keep back the tears
waiting to fall(99)

Words are longings—longings for belonging and belonging for longings. The absence of desire makes a man dead while its presence puts life into him. Hamid knows well how to use the abstract concept of desire. He skillfully translates the abstract concept of desire and makes it a real phenomenon. The ontology of desire

proves to be a magic in the hands of Hamid who makes it visible to the readers who feel its presence in their hearts. Indeed, the poet in Hamid is lively and enthusiastic in his approach to poetry, which in his hands, gets a Hindustani flavour. The fragrance of Urdu idiom gives him a refined, humble and polite tone, which enlarges his heart that makes him honest in his poetic expression. G.J.V. Prasad is right when he states: Syed Ali Hamid's poetry practices "the alchemy of souls" with stirring success, enchanting our minds into periods of golden calm and quietly intense storms. The intimacy that the words ensnare you in with ease, holding up mirrors to your own life, is made possible by his consummate control" (Blurb).

Works Cited

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"Jaydeep Sarangi in Conversation with S.A. Hamid." *Poetcrit* 28.2 (July 2015) 23-26.